

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Narziyev Nosir Baxshilloevich

DASTURIY TA'MINOT SIFATINI BAHOLASH

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/MAY

